

20IND11 MetHyInfra

Deliverable D5: Technical report on the newly implemented CFD model of high-pressure hydrogen flows in OpenFOAM taking the most important influences of real gas effects into account

DELIVERABLE D5

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<p>Summary</p> <p>This deliverable was written as part of activity 3.3.4 from the EMPIR Metrology infrastructure for high-pressure gas and liquified hydrogen flows (MetHyInfra) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2021 and focused on providing metrological infrastructure and traceability for high pressure hydrogen flow meter calibration (1000 bar / 3.6 kg/min), fuel cells applications (4 kg/h, 30 bar) and liquid hydrogen. For more details about this project please visit methyinfra.ptb.de.</p> <p>This deliverable is a technical report on the newly implemented CFD model of high-pressure hydrogen flows in OpenFOAM taking the most important influences of real gas effects into account. It is based on the report "Suitable modeling approaches for the most important influences of real gas effects in high-pressure hydrogen flows" [14] and on the journal publication "Derivation and validation of a reference data-based real gas model for hydrogen" [16].</p>		
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1 Introduction

Hydrogen is a promising energy carrier for the usage in climate-neutral applications in industry and transport. It is widely regarded as a potential solution for the future of energy security and sustainability [9]. Due to its low volumetric energy density, gaseous hydrogen needs to be stored at considerably high pressures (up to 1000 bar). To monitor hydrogen consumption, a verifiable flow measurement is required. Critical flow Venturi nozzles (CFVNs) are a state-of-the-art secondary standard gas flow meter. For precisely predicting the mass flow rate of high-pressure hydrogen through CFVNs in numerical simulations, an accurate real gas model is required. Such a model needs to include all relevant real gas effects within the required pressure and temperature range, which is for CFVNs – based on simulation results – typically between 150 K and 400 K.

To determine the relevant real gas effects in high-pressure hydrogen flows, it is important to understand the difference between ideal and real gases. In an ideal gas, particles have no volume, collisions between particles are elastic, and there are no intermolecular forces between them. In contrast, in a real gas, particles have a volume, collisions are non-elastic, and intermolecular forces are existing. Under standard conditions for pressure and temperature, hydrogen behaves like an ideal gas, i. e., it follows the rules of the ideal gas law. However, in specific ranges for pressure and temperature, the real gas hydrogen deviates from the ideal gas behavior leading to erroneous predictions of its thermodynamic and transport properties. At high pressure, the distance between gas particles becomes smaller and particle interactions as well as the particle volume are relevant and cannot be neglected as in the case of an ideal gas. At low temperatures, gas particles have less kinetic energy so that energy losses during particle collisions are important to consider. Consequently, real gas effects especially appear at high pressures and low temperatures. For that reason, the ideal gas law is not sufficient to describe high-pressure hydrogen flows precisely. In hydrogen flows through critical nozzles at high pressures, real gas effects, like van der Waals forces, compressibility effects, variable specific heat capacities, and the Joule-Thomson effect, can occur and therefore need to be captured by a real gas model.

This technical report is structured as follows:

In Section 2, different equation of state (EoS) models are discussed and correlation equations for density and relevant thermodynamic properties are presented for the usage in numerical simulations. In Section 3, the two transport properties, dynamic viscosity and thermal conductivity, are introduced and their correlation equations for the efficient integration in numerical software are provided. Sec-

tion 4 is concerned with the influence of the real gas behavior on two important flow parameters, namely the critical flow factor and the speed of sound. In Section 5, the implementation of the developed correlation equations for the thermodynamic and transport properties (constituting the new real gas model for hydrogen) into the structure of OpenFOAM [7] is presented. Furthermore, the implemented real gas model is validated using a test case of a CFVN and is made available in an open source online GitLab repository.

2 Equation of State (EoS)

An EoS is a thermodynamic equation that relates the physical properties of a fluid, like pressure p , temperature T , and density ρ , with each other and can generally be written as:

$$f(p, T, \rho) = 0. \quad (1)$$

In the following, different EoS models are presented and compared.

2.1 Ideal gas EoS

The ideal gas EoS is given as follows:

$$p \cdot V_m = R \cdot T \quad \text{with} \quad V_m = \frac{M}{\rho}, \quad (2)$$

where p , T , V_m , ρ , M , and R are pressure, temperature, molar volume, density, molar mass, and the universal gas constant, respectively. It is a good approximation for gases at low pressures and moderate temperatures. In order to fully describe the behavior of hydrogen at high pressure, the ideal gas EoS is not sufficient. Thus, in the following, different real gas EoS models are shown that can be used for simulating hydrogen flows within the MetHyInfra project.

2.2 Cubic EoS

An extension of the ideal gas EoS is represented by cubic EoS models owing their name to the fact that they can be formulated in a cubic function of the molar volume. All cubic EoS approaches are based on the van der Waals EoS and include parameters to allow for intermolecular forces and the effect of particle volume.

One representative is the Peng-Robinson EoS [8] that is given by the formulation:

$$\left(p + \frac{\gamma \cdot A}{V_m^2 + 2B \cdot V_m - B^2} \right) \cdot (V_m - B) = R \cdot T, \quad (3)$$

where the parameters A , B , and γ are substance-specific and can be expressed in terms of the critical properties and the acentric factor. Comparing this equation to the one of the ideal gas in Eq. (2) shows additional terms expressed in pressure and molar volume considering the intermolecular forces as well as the particle volume, respectively. The Peng-Robinson EoS is the only preinstalled real gas EoS in the OpenFOAM software.

2.3 Empirical fundamental EoS

Empirical fundamental EoS models are very accurate expressions of the EoS for pure fluids in terms of empirical correlations based on experimental data. They are often formulated in the reduced form of the Helmholtz free energy α :

$$\alpha(\delta, \tau) = \frac{a(\rho, T)}{R \cdot T} \quad \text{with} \quad a(\rho, T) = u - T \cdot s, \quad \delta = \frac{\rho}{\rho_c}, \quad \text{and} \quad \tau = \frac{T_c}{T}. \quad (4)$$

Here, a , u , and s depict the Helmholtz free energy, internal energy, and entropy, respectively. The reduced density δ and inverse reduced temperature τ are scaled with the critical density ρ_c and critical temperature T_c of the considered gas, respectively.

The reduced Helmholtz free energy is typically separated into an ideal α^0 and a residual part α^r :

$$\alpha(\delta, \tau) = \alpha^0(\delta, \tau) + \alpha^r(\delta, \tau). \quad (5)$$

Leachman et al. [4] developed an empirical fundamental EoS based on the Helmholtz free energy for parahydrogen, normal hydrogen, and orthohydrogen for pressures up to 2000 MPa and temperatures up to 1000 K. The expressions for the ideal and residual parts of the reduced Helmholtz energy are as follows:

$$\alpha^0(\delta, \tau) = \ln(\delta) + 1.5 \ln(\tau) + a_1 + a_2 \tau + \sum_{k=3}^N a_k \ln(1 - e^{b_k \tau}), \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha^r(\delta, \tau) = & \sum_{i=1}^l N_i \delta^{d_i} \tau^{t_i} + \sum_{i=l+1}^m N_i \delta^{d_i} \tau^{t_i} e^{-\delta^{p_i}} \\ & + \sum_{i=m+1}^n N_i \delta^{d_i} \tau^{t_i} e^{\varphi_i(\delta - D_i)^2 + \beta_i(\tau - \gamma_i)^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The parameters a_k and b_k for the ideal part as well as N_i , d_i , t_i , p_i , φ_i , β_i , D_i , and γ_i for the residual part are optimized according to a nonlinear regression of calculated ideal gas heat capacity data from literature as well as experimental thermodynamic and caloric data for hydrogen, respectively.

The ideal contribution to the reduced Helmholtz free energy in Eq. (6) is physically motivated based on an ideal gas heat capacity equation. The residual contribution in Eq. (7) is composed of three summations, where the first summation is a simple polynomial containing seven terms. The two terms in the second summation contain an exponential density component to improve the prediction in liquid and critical-region properties. The third summation contains five modified Gaussian bell-shaped terms to model the critical region more precisely.

Once the reduced Helmholtz free energy is calculated, other thermodynamic properties, i. e. internal energy, enthalpy, entropy, heat capacity, speed of sound, etc., can be calculated directly, as derived by Span et al. [11] for nitrogen. The required derivatives for hydrogen can be found in the work by Ding et al. [2].

2.4 Correlation equations for density and thermodynamic properties

The correlations for the reduced Helmholtz energy (and accordingly for the thermodynamic properties) in Eqs. (6) and (7) contain exponential terms as well as terms with real number exponents that are more time-consuming to calculate in a computer system compared to simple arithmetic operations. Since the thermophysical properties need to be calculated on every mesh node in every time step in a computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulation, the direct implementation of those equations would result in a drastic slowdown of the computation. Therefore, new accurate correlations using simple terms have been developed in [16]. These approximations are suitable for efficient usage in CFD simulations.

In the thermophysical model of [7], the two independent intensive thermodynamic properties are pressure and temperature, from which other properties are computed. However, the EoS model as well as the transport models for hydrogen are formulated explicitly in density and temperature (or their reduced forms). Hence, the density needs to be calculated iteratively from pressure and temperature by solving the following equation

$$p = \rho R_M T Z = \rho R_M T \left[1 + \delta \left(\frac{\partial \alpha^r}{\partial \delta} \right)_\tau \right] \quad \text{with} \quad R_M = \frac{R}{M}, \quad (8)$$

where $(\partial \alpha^r / \partial \delta)_\tau$ and R are the first partial derivative of α^r with respect to δ and the universal gas constant, respectively. Thus, the density is determined in a pre-processing step using the iterative regula falsi method with starting values for density based on the Peng-Robinson EoS model. The direct implementation of this iterative calculation procedure, including the aforementioned complicated form of α^r , is highly time-consuming. Hence, the density is approximated by a polynomial representation in pressure and temperature only using simple exponents, e. g. integers or half-integers. For the determination of appropriate exponents in

pressure and temperature, the form of the virial EoS is used as a starting point. Further details on the derivation of the polynomial representation for the density can be found in [16]. The final form of the reduced density $\delta = \rho/\rho_c$ is given by

$$\delta(\psi, \tau) = \left[\sum_{j=1}^{24} n_j \psi^{p_j} \tau^{t_j} \right]^{-1}, \quad (9)$$

where $\psi = p/p_c$ and $\tau = T_c/T$ are the reduced pressure and the inverse of the reduced temperature, respectively. The values for the correlation coefficients n_j and the exponents p_j and t_j , $j = 1, \dots, 24$, are summarized in Table 1. The method on how the correlation coefficients n_j are determined is provided in [16]. The mean and maximum percentage error between the approximated density according to Eq. (9) and the density based on the EoS model by [4] are 0.0133% and 0.107%, respectively, in the considered pressure and temperature range between 0.1 and 1000 bar and 150 and 400 K, respectively. The developed polynomial representation of density serves as the input for other thermophysical property correlations.

Similarly to density, correlations for the specific internal energy u , specific enthalpy h , speed of sound w , specific heat capacity at constant volume c_v , specific heat capacity at constant pressure c_p , temperature derivative of heat capacity at constant pressure $\partial c_p/\partial T$, and specific entropy s are derived in [16]. They can all be calculated using the following equation:

$$f(\delta, \tau) = \sum_{j=1}^{N_f} n_{f,j} \delta^{d_{f,j}} \tau^{t_{f,j}}, \quad (10)$$

where f denotes the respective thermophysical property and the parameters N_f , $n_{f,j}$, $d_{f,j}$, and $t_{f,j}$ are given in Tables 2, 3, and 4 (left part). The mean and maximum percentage errors of the correlations for the presented thermodynamic properties in comparison with those based on the model by [4] are all below 0.041% and 0.23% in the considered pressure and temperature range, respectively. Thus, all relevant thermodynamic properties (including density) can be expressed as a function of pressure and temperature that is adequate for an accurate and time-efficient implementation in OpenFOAM.

j	n_j^a	p_j	t_j
1	3.296 64	-1	-1
2	$-2.965 03 \times 10^{-4}$	-0.5	-1
3	$-2.712 93 \times 10^{-3}$	0	-1
4	$-3.079 42 \times 10^{-4}$	0.5	-1
5	$1.083 65 \times 10^{-4}$	1	-1
6	$-5.787 55 \times 10^{-7}$	2	-1
7	$-2.999 25 \times 10^{-4}$	-1	0
8	$4.802 31 \times 10^{-3}$	-0.5	0
9	$3.523 93 \times 10^{-1}$	0	0
10	$1.079 14 \times 10^{-2}$	0.5	0
11	$-3.786 48 \times 10^{-3}$	1	0
12	$1.873 03 \times 10^{-5}$	2	0
13	$1.452 74 \times 10^{-2}$	-1	1
14	$-2.000 07 \times 10^{-1}$	-0.5	1
15	$-5.229 84 \times 10^{-1}$	0	1
16	$-2.527 58 \times 10^{-1}$	0.5	1
17	$5.076 39 \times 10^{-2}$	1	1
18	$-2.220 19 \times 10^{-4}$	2	1
19	$-2.394 96 \times 10^{-1}$	-1	2
20	3.130 49	-0.5	2
21	-5.521 93	0	2
22	2.390 76	0.5	2
23	$-2.624 58 \times 10^{-1}$	1	2
24	$8.051 04 \times 10^{-4}$	2	2

^a see Eq. (9) ($\rho = \delta\rho_c$)

Table 1: Correlation coefficients for density ρ .

j	$n_{u,j}$ [kJ/kg] ^a	$n_{h,j}$ [kJ/kg] ^a	$n_{w,j}$ [m/s] ^a	d_j ^b	t_j ^c
1	1.66326×10^2	3.03062×10^2	-2.71181×10^1	0	-1
2	2.03694×10^3	2.03649×10^3	7.76265×10^2	0	-0.5
3	-8.77694×10^3	-8.77388×10^3	-1.522395×10^3	0	0
4	1.41406×10^4	1.41309×10^4	2.81681×10^3	0	0.5
5	-7.57078×10^3	-7.55996×10^3	-1.67760×10^3	0	1
6	6.40399×10^1	6.36698×10^1	1.32645	0.5	-1
7	-7.07774×10^2	-6.98573×10^2	-1.72587×10^1	0.5	-0.5
8	2.89833×10^3	2.81602×10^3	4.33246×10^1	0.5	0
9	-5.21393×10^3	-4.92031×10^3	1.09521×10^2	0.5	0.5
10	3.49142×10^3	3.15378×10^3	-3.58364×10^2	0.5	1
11	-1.43105×10^2	-1.35344×10^2	-2.62137×10^1	1	-1
12	1.70326×10^3	1.97628×10^3	3.60253×10^2	1	-0.5
13	-7.20227×10^3	-7.97925×10^3	-7.38312×10^2	1	0
14	1.26160×10^4	1.30428×10^4	6.20799×10^2	1	0.5
15	-8.48406×10^3	-8.35712×10^3	8.08972×10^1	1	1
16	1.90092×10^2	1.99078×10^2	1.24475×10^1	2	-1
17	-2.10618×10^3	-2.19914×10^3	-2.20683×10^2	2	-0.5
18	8.71287×10^3	9.30693×10^3	1.20546×10^3	2	0
19	-1.58225×10^4	-1.68244×10^4	-1.84073×10^3	2	0.5
20	1.07088×10^4	1.11697×10^4	6.56728×10^2	2	1
21	-1.18744×10^2	-1.24085×10^2	5.65469	3	-1
22	1.34594×10^3	1.44531×10^3	1.45714×10^1	3	-0.5
23	-5.59308×10^3	-6.06570×10^3	-3.55818×10^2	3	0
24	1.01808×10^4	1.10697×10^4	9.45804×10^2	3	0.5
25	-6.90269×10^3	-7.46762×10^3	-4.29182×10^2	3	1
26	2.07213×10^1	1.93108×10^1	-6.81222	4	-1
27	-2.45435×10^2	-2.45916×10^2	5.41650×10^1	4	-0.5
28	1.05468×10^3	1.10788×10^3	-1.26560×10^2	4	0
29	-1.96079×10^3	-2.09574×10^3	9.53261×10^1	4	0.5
30	1.35198×10^3	1.46399×10^3	-5.12543×10^1	4	1

^a see Eq. (10)

^b $d_j = d_{u,j} = d_{h,j} = d_{w,j}$

^c $t_j = t_{u,j} = t_{h,j} = t_{w,j}$

Table 2: Correlation coefficients for specific internal energy u , specific enthalpy h , and speed of sound w .

j	$n_{c_v,j}$ [kJ/(kg·K)] ^a	$n_{c_p,j}$ [kJ/(kg·K)] ^a	$n_{\partial c_p/\partial T,j}$ [kJ/(kg·K ²)] ^a	d_j ^d	t_j ^c
1	2.484 33	2.517 85	$-3.191 88 \times 10^{-2}$	0	-1
2	$-2.981 39 \times 10^1$	$-3.022 00 \times 10^1$	$4.046 56 \times 10^{-1}$	0	-0.5
3	$1.396 26 \times 10^2$	$1.455 86 \times 10^2$	-1.865 51	0	0
4	$-2.336 02 \times 10^2$	$-2.372 70 \times 10^2$	3.635 55	0	0.5
5	$1.395 34 \times 10^2$	$1.422 64 \times 10^2$	-2.425 21	0	1
6	$-1.057 38 \times 10^{-1}$	-1.092 65	$4.082 31 \times 10^{-2}$	0.5	-1
7	1.198 05	$1.314 52 \times 10^1$	$-4.800 87 \times 10^{-1}$	0.5	-0.5
8	-5.068 75	$-5.901 52 \times 10^1$	2.104 61	0.5	0
9	9.502 35	$1.170 76 \times 10^2$	-4.078 14	0.5	0.5
10	-6.679 22	$-8.666 93 \times 10^1$	2.949 90	0.5	1
11	$3.080 25 \times 10^{-1}$	2.776 12	$-1.061 55 \times 10^{-1}$	1	-1
12	-3.606 05	$-3.366 60 \times 10^1$	1.265 75	1	-0.5
13	$1.615 49 \times 10^1$	$1.521 08 \times 10^2$	-5.643 40	1	0
14	$-3.100 83 \times 10^1$	$-3.051 73 \times 10^2$	$1.118 96 \times 10^1$	1	0.5
15	$2.293 84 \times 10^1$	$2.411 13 \times 10^2$	-8.402 44	1	1
16	$-3.950 08 \times 10^{-1}$	-2.521 10	$8.692 20 \times 10^{-2}$	2	-1
17	4.528 39	$3.064 12 \times 10^1$	-1.036 98	2	-0.5
18	$-1.956 33 \times 10^1$	$-1.380 74 \times 10^2$	4.588 75	2	0
19	$3.828 58 \times 10^1$	$2.729 39 \times 10^2$	-8.937 39	2	0.5
20	$-2.856 28 \times 10^1$	$-2.048 64 \times 10^2$	6.494 48	2	1
21	$2.588 76 \times 10^{-1}$	1.085 94	$-3.040 07 \times 10^{-2}$	3	-1
22	-2.917 03	$-1.343 29 \times 10^1$	$3.746 29 \times 10^{-1}$	3	-0.5
23	$1.229 03 \times 10^1$	$6.108 07 \times 10^1$	-1.680 19	3	0
24	$-2.309 72 \times 10^1$	$-1.195 35 \times 10^2$	3.245 93	3	0.5
25	$1.664 39 \times 10^1$	$8.503 22 \times 10^1$	-2.271 79	3	1
26	$-5.843 33 \times 10^{-2}$	$-1.418 53 \times 10^{-1}$	$1.280 76 \times 10^{-3}$	4	-1
27	$6.546 12 \times 10^{-1}$	1.875 79	$-2.480 25 \times 10^{-2}$	4	-0.5
28	-2.731 47	-8.994 91	$1.392 61 \times 10^{-1}$	4	0
29	5.059 93	$1.818 44 \times 10^1$	$-3.025 80 \times 10^{-1}$	4	0.5
30	-3.564 15	$-1.290 59 \times 10^1$	$2.204 47 \times 10^{-1}$	4	1

^a see Eq. (10)

^b $d_j = d_{c_v,j} = d_{c_p,j} = d_{\partial c_p/\partial T,j}$

^c $t_j = t_{c_v,j} = t_{c_p,j} = t_{\partial c_p/\partial T,j}$

Table 3: Correlation coefficients for specific heat capacity at constant volume c_v , specific heat capacity at constant pressure c_p , and temperature derivative of heat capacity at constant pressure $\partial c_p/\partial T$.

j	$n_{s,j}$ [kJ/(kg·K)] ^a	$d_{s,j}$	$t_{s,j}$	$n_{\mu,j}$ [μkg/(m·s)] ^a	$d_{\mu,j}$	$t_{\mu,j}$
1	-4.63086×10^{-7}	-2	-1	7.74548×10^{-1}	0	0
2	4.38983×10^{-6}	-2	-0.5	1.29239	0	-1
3	-1.04137×10^{-5}	-2	0	-6.84212×10^{-2}	0	-2
4	3.17938×10^{-5}	-1.5	-1	3.48747×10^{-3}	0	-3
5	-4.03693×10^{-4}	-1.5	-0.5	-7.67423×10^{-5}	0	-4
6	1.18030×10^{-3}	-1.5	0	-1.46087×10^4	1	6
7	-3.67985×10^{-4}	-1	-1	1.66934×10^4	1	5
8	1.23039×10^{-2}	-1	-0.5	-7.65723×10^3	1	4
9	-5.22620×10^{-2}	-1	0	1.56406×10^3	1	3
10	-1.07799×10^{-2}	-0.5	-1	-1.67026	1	2
11	-1.48187×10^{-1}	-0.5	-0.5	-7.66929×10^1	1	1
12	1.35461	-0.5	0	2.09739×10^1	1	0
13	-5.67119×10^{-1}	0	-1	-2.83919	1	-1
14	1.22575×10^1	0	-0.5	2.21891×10^{-1}	1	-2
15	1.31791×10^1	0	0	-9.69993×10^{-3}	1	-3
16	-1.54770	0.5	-1	1.81478×10^{-4}	1	-4
17	-1.22244×10^{-1}	0.5	-0.5	8.28934×10^{-1}	2	0
18	-2.47217×10^1	0.5	0	2.65215×10^{-2}	2	-1
19	4.21846	1	-1	1.36338×10^{-3}	2	-2
20	-5.09725	1	-0.5	1.58944×10^{-1}	4	1
21	1.90369×10^1	1	0	-6.42377×10^{-3}	4	0
22	-5.07760	1.5	-1	3.02064×10^{-4}	4	-1
23	1.12461×10^1	1.5	-0.5	5.97459×10^{-2}	6	2
24	-1.63656×10^1	1.5	0	-4.25572×10^{-2}	6	1
25	2.11855	2	-1	4.36490×10^{-3}	6	0
26	-5.94803	2	-0.5	4.56887×10^{-2}	8	3
27	6.21797	2	0	-3.15245×10^{-2}	8	2
28	-	-	-	9.20430×10^{-3}	8	1

^a see Eq. (10)

Table 4: Correlation coefficients for specific entropy s and dynamic viscosity μ .

3 Transport properties

The three main transport properties in fluid dynamics are dynamic viscosity, thermal conductivity, and mass diffusivity corresponding to the transfer of momentum, energy, and mass, respectively. They appear as proportionality factors in the Newton's law of viscosity, the Fourier's law of heat conduction, and the Fick's law of molecular diffusion, respectively. Since no gas mixture but only pure hydrogen is considered in this project, the mass diffusivity is not relevant and will therefore not be considered in this section.

3.1 Dynamic viscosity

The dynamic viscosity of a fluid describes the resistance to deformation at a given shear force. Based on the kinetic theory of gases, the dynamic viscosity is only a function of temperature for dilute gases. For ideal gases, Sutherland's law [12] can be used to predict the dynamic viscosity μ_s as follows:

$$\mu_s = \frac{A_s \cdot T^{\frac{3}{2}}}{T + T_s}, \quad (11)$$

where A_s and T_s are substance-specific constants. However, at high pressures and consequently high densities, the dynamic viscosity is also dependent on pressure or density, respectively. Muzny et al. [5] developed an experimentally-based correlation for the dynamic viscosity of hydrogen for temperatures up to 1000 K and pressures up to 200 MPa using the following approach

$$\mu(\rho, T) = \mu_0(T) + \Delta\mu_{\text{excess}}(\rho, T) + \Delta\mu_c(\rho, T), \quad (12)$$

where μ_0 is the viscosity contribution for the limit of zero density, which is comparable with μ_s . It reads as

$$\mu_0(T) = \frac{0.021357 \cdot \sqrt{M \cdot T}}{\sigma^2 \cdot S^*} \quad \text{with} \quad \ln(S^*) = \sum_{i=0}^4 \hat{a}_i (\ln(T^*))^i \quad (13)$$

with the reduced temperature $T^* = k_B T / \varepsilon$ and $\varepsilon / k_B = 30.41$ K and $\sigma = 0.297$ nm. The excess term $\Delta\mu_{\text{excess}}$ accounts for the increase in viscosity above the zero density value at elevated density. It reads as

$$\Delta\mu_{\text{excess}}(\rho, T) = \mu_1(T) \cdot \rho + \Delta\mu_h(\rho, T) \quad (14)$$

with

$$\mu_1(T) = \frac{N_A \sigma^3}{M} \cdot \sum_{i=0}^6 \hat{b}_i (T^*)^{-1} \cdot \mu_0(T) \quad (15)$$

and

$$\Delta\mu_h(\rho, T) = \hat{c}_1 \rho_r^2 \cdot e^{\left(\hat{c}_2 T_r + \hat{c}_3 T_r^{-1} + \frac{\hat{c}_4 \rho_r^2}{\hat{c}_5 + T_r} + \hat{c}_6 \rho_r^6\right)}. \quad (16)$$

Here, M , σ , T^* , N_A , ρ_r , and T_r are the molar mass, length scaling parameter, reduced temperature, Avogadro constant, scaled density, and scaled temperature, respectively. Eq. (15) is corrected according to the erratum in [6]. The last term $\Delta\mu_c$ considers the behavior of viscosity near the critical point. As this contribution only affects a small temperature and density range near the critical point, the authors omitted this term and did not consider the small region near the critical point. Since the critical nozzle flow in this project will not reach close to the critical point, this approach is suitable for the flow simulation.

3.2 Thermal conductivity

The thermal conductivity is a measure of a material's ability to conduct heat. Similar to the dynamic viscosity, the thermal conductivity only depends on temperature for small densities. In OpenFOAM, an expression for the thermal conductivity k_s of an ideal gas is based on the dynamic viscosity by Sutherland using a modified Eucken equation

$$k_s = \mu_s (1.32 \cdot c_v + 1.77 \cdot R_M) \quad \text{with} \quad R_M = \frac{R}{M}, \quad (17)$$

where c_v and R_M are the specific heat capacity at constant volume and the specific gas constant, respectively. By analogy to the dynamic viscosity, the density dependence becomes relevant for high pressures and densities.

Assael et al. [1] developed a correlation of the thermal conductivity of hydrogen fitted to experimental data in the temperature and pressure range of up to 1000 K and 100 MPa, respectively. The thermal conductivity is expressed as the sum of three independent contributions as

$$k(\rho, T) = k_0(T) + \Delta k_{\text{excess}}(\rho, T) + \Delta k_c(\rho, T). \quad (18)$$

These terms are similarly defined to those in Eq. (12) for the dynamic viscosity. The first two terms read as

$$k_0(T) = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^6 A_{1,i} \cdot \tau^{-i}}{\sum_{i=0}^3 A_{2,i} \cdot \tau^{-i}} \quad (19)$$

and

$$\Delta k_{\text{excess}}(\rho, T) = \sum_{i=1}^5 \delta^i (B_{1,i} + B_{2,i} \cdot \tau^{-1}) \quad (20)$$

with the correlation coefficients $A_{1,i}$, $A_{2,i}$, $B_{1,i}$, and $B_{2,i}$. The last term, the critical enhancement term Δk_c , is omitted for the thermal conductivity correlation because the critical temperature for normal hydrogen ($T_c = 33.145$ K) is well below the considered fitting range (150 to 400 K).

3.3 Correlation equations for transport properties

The transport equations by [5] (Eqs. (12) to (16)) for the dynamic viscosity contain exponential terms that require more calculation time compared to simpler polynomial terms. Therefore, for an efficient usage in computational flow simulations, the dynamic viscosity μ is also approximated according to Eq. (10). The derived correlation coefficients $n_{\mu,j}$ and exponents $d_{\mu,j}$ and $t_{\mu,j}$ are listed in Table 4 (right part). The mean and maximum percentage error between the approximated dynamic viscosity and that based on the model by [5] are 0.0008% and 0.014% in the considered pressure range (0.1 to 1000 bar) and temperature range (150 to 400 K), respectively.

As the correlations for the thermal conductivity by [1] in Eqs. (18) to (20) only contain exponents with integer values, the expression for the thermal conductivity does not require any modification.

4 Flow properties

The real gas behavior also has an influence on relevant flow properties and their calculation. Therefore, two important flow parameters, namely the critical flow factor and the speed of sound, will be discussed hereafter.

4.1 Critical flow factor

The mass flow rate in a critical nozzle can be calculated as

$$\dot{m} = C_D \cdot C^* \cdot A^* \cdot \frac{p_0}{\sqrt{R_M \cdot T_0}}, \quad (21)$$

where p_0 and T_0 are the stagnation pressure and stagnation temperature, respectively. The quantities C_D , A^* , and C^* are the discharge coefficient, the critical area, and the critical flow factor, respectively. The critical flow factor C^* considers the real gas effects of a one-dimensional isentropic nozzle flow from the inlet to the nozzle throat and can be determined as follows

$$C^* = \rho^* \cdot u^* \cdot \frac{\sqrt{R_M \cdot T_0}}{p_0}, \quad (22)$$

where ρ^* and u^* are the density and velocity in the nozzle throat or in the critical area. Using the isentropic relation and the EoS for an ideal gas, Eq. (22) simplifies to

$$C_{\text{ideal}}^* = \sqrt{\kappa \left(\frac{2}{\kappa + 1} \right)^{\frac{\kappa+1}{\kappa-1}}} \quad \text{with} \quad \kappa = \frac{c_p}{c_v}. \quad (23)$$

Here, κ is the isentropic exponent and c_p and c_v are the specific heat capacities at constant pressure and volume, respectively. For a perfect gas, which is an ideal gas with constant specific heat capacities, the isentropic exponent κ is approximately 1.4 for hydrogen and thus the critical flow factor C^* becomes circa 0.68473.

However, in case of a real gas, the isentropic relation and the EoS for an ideal gas are not valid and therefore, the critical flow factor cannot be expressed in this explicit form. The real critical flow factor needs to be determined iteratively for the isentropic and thus adiabatic flow process between the inlet and the throat of the nozzle. Therefore, the specific entropy and the specific total enthalpy between those two points need to be constant yielding a set of two equations:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} s(p_0, T_0) &= s(p^*, T^*) \\ h(p_0, T_0) &= h(p^*, T^*) + \frac{1}{2}u^{*2} \end{aligned} \right\} p^*, T^* \rightarrow \rho^*, u^* \rightarrow C_{\text{real}}^* \quad (24)$$

The inlet stagnation quantities (index 0) are given whereas the critical quantities (index *) are unknown. The specific entropy and enthalpy can be calculated based on the real gas model in use. The critical velocity is equal to the local speed of sound in a one-dimensional critical nozzle that can also be determined with the real gas model. Hence, this is a system of two equations with two unknowns p^* and T^* , from which the real critical flow function can be determined. In the works of Schley et al. [10] and Ding et al. [2] two iteration procedures for the calculation of C_{real}^* are demonstrated.

4.2 Speed of sound

The speed of sound w , which is relevant for the calculation of the Mach number or of the critical flow factor as discussed in the preceding paragraph, is given as follows:

$$w = \sqrt{\kappa \cdot \frac{p}{\rho}}. \quad (25)$$

For an ideal gas, the isentropic exponent represents the ratio of specific heat capacities:

$$\kappa_{\text{ideal}} = \frac{c_p}{c_v} \rightarrow w = \sqrt{\frac{c_p}{c_v} \cdot \frac{p}{\rho}}. \quad (26)$$

In order to calculate the speed of sound for real gases, the isentropic exponent needs to be changed to

$$\kappa_{\text{real}} = \frac{c_p}{c_v} \cdot \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial \rho} \right)_T \cdot \frac{\rho}{p} \rightarrow w = \sqrt{\frac{c_p}{c_v} \cdot \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial \rho} \right)_T}. \quad (27)$$

The corresponding formulas can be derived from the work on isentropic exponents for real gases by Kouremenos and Antonopoulos [3].

5 Implementation of the real gas model in OpenFOAM

For the actual usage of the new real gas model of hydrogen within CFD simulations, the developed correlations are implemented into the structure of OpenFOAM. An overview of the OpenFOAM folder structure for the integration of thermophysical models is depicted in Fig. 1. The core of the implementation occurs in

Figure 1: Overview of the new real gas model in the OpenFOAM folder structure

the `/mySpecie` folder, where the correlation equations are directly implemented. The thermodynamic properties related to the EoS model are integrated into the `/LeachmanH2Gas` and `/H2Thermo` folders, whereas the transport properties are incorporated in the `/H2Transport` folder. In order to introduce the newly defined real gas model to the OpenFOAM thermophysical library, a new entry is added to the `psiThermo` class.

In [7], the function object applies the following equation for the Mach number calculation

$$M_{\text{OF}} = \frac{|u|}{\sqrt{\kappa \frac{p}{\rho}}} \quad \text{with} \quad \kappa = \frac{c_p}{c_v}, \quad (28)$$

where u is the velocity of the flow and the isentropic exponent κ represents the ratio of specific heat capacities. This formula only holds true for ideal gases as the denominator depicts the speed of sound using the ideal isentropic exponent. For the implementation of the Mach number for real gas hydrogen, the correlation of the speed of sound w (see Table 2) can directly be used so that the expression

$$M_{\text{real}} = \frac{|u|}{w} \quad (29)$$

is integrated in the `/MachNoRealH2` folder. The newly implemented real gas model for hydrogen based on the REFPROP database into OpenFOAM [7] can be found at an open source online GitLab repository hosted at Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB) [13]. The repository also contains tutorial test cases using the new real gas model for hydrogen.

As a validation test case, a toroidal CFVN was investigated in the work by Weiss et al. [15] regarding the ideal discharge coefficient at different Reynolds numbers. The results of the new real gas model were in best accordance with experimental data, compared with those of the ideal gas model, the Peng-Robinson EoS model, as well as with the standard curves of the ISO 9300. Altogether, an accurate and time-efficient real gas model of hydrogen was made available in the MethHyInfra project for the application in numerical simulations within a wide pressure range (0.1 to 1000 bar) and temperature range (150 to 400 K).

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